
VICE PRINCIPALS' WORK BEHAVIOURS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE: THE MEDIATION OF PRINCIPALS' DISTRIBUTIVE JUSTICE ON VICE PRINCIPALS' JOB PERFORMANCE AND ABSENTEEISM BEHAVIOURS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Distributive justice is a dimension of principals' organizational justice which has hardly been explored in relation to vice principals' work behaviours in Anambra State. This study therefore employed the correlational research design to ascertain how principals' distributive justice in Anambra State could impact vice principals' work behaviours, especially vice principals' job performance and absenteeism. One research question and one hypothesis were postulated. The population of the study was all the principals and vice principals in the 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. A sample of 532 vice principals, comprising 266 vice principals' administration and 266 vice principals' academics was drawn, using the census sampling technique. Two instruments namely, Principals' Organizational Justice Scale for Vice Principals (POJSVP) and Vice Principals' Work Behaviours Scale (VPWBS) were used for data collection. POJSVP was adapted, while VPWBS was constructed by the researchers. To ascertain the face validity of the instruments, they were submitted to three research experts in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka. After the validation of the instruments by the research experts, they were pilot-tested on twenty (20) public secondary school vice principals in Enugu State. The Cronbach alpha reliability test was used in the data analysis to determine the internal reliability coefficient of the two instruments. This yielded an average reliability coefficient of 0.86, an indication that the instruments were suitable for the study. A total of 532 copies of the instruments were administered on the target population, with the help of four research assistants, in the six education zones in Anambra State. A total of 521 (98%) copies were completely filled by the respondents and retrieved. The simple regression analysis was used. It was found out that principals' distributive justice had a moderate predictive value on vice principals' work behaviours. This value was found to be significant to vice principals' work behaviours. It was recommended that principals in secondary schools in Anambra State should consider vice principals in the distribution of the school resources and reward systems, especially in proportion to vice principals' contributions to the schools, in order to enhance vice principals' work behaviours in Anambra State.

Keywords: Vice Principals, Work Behaviors, Public Secondary Schools, Anambra State, Principals' Distributive Justice, Job Performance, Absenteeism Behaviors

Introduction

Vice principals are teachers appointed by the government or school board (a government agency on education) to assist principals in the overall running of the schools. Vice principals are therefore one of the core leaders of the secondary schools whose roles are crucial to the achievement of the school goals. Vice principals are simply the bridge between the principals and the rest of the secondary school members. As the bridge between the principals' vision and the staff who help to realize this vision (Ho, Kang and Shaari, 2020), between principals and students, between students and teachers, parents and the school, the education ministry and the school (van Niekerk, 2022) and between other educational professionals and the school community (Shewchuck and Farley-Ripple, 2022), there is no doubt that they can significantly influence every facet of the school building and beyond (Irvine, 2022) through their work behaviours. This shows that vice principals are one of the core leaders of the school organization whose behaviours affect the behaviours of other school members. It implies that the work behaviours of vice principals in secondary schools in Anambra State can impact the attitudes, behaviours and dispositions of the students, teachers, parents and other school members towards one another and towards the achievement of the goals of the secondary schools in Anambra State. It entails that principals in secondary schools in Anambra State should understand the importance of vice principals' work behaviours to them as colleagues/partners in their school leadership and in the entire school system so as to enhance vice principals' work behaviours.

Work behaviours of employees have been established as the most crucial aspect of their workplace relationship which affects the customers' and other stakeholders' interest, disposition, willingness, readiness, participation and contribution to the success of the organizations. Work behaviours are those things employees do while performing the works they are assigned to do in the organizations and interacting with other members of the organizations. Rouch (2023) sees work behaviours as actions, conducts and performance of individuals within a work environment. It simply consists of the observable (physical) and unobservable (mental or emotional) components of people's behaviours, while working in an organization. In the context of this study, vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State are vice principals' physical and emotional reactions to other school members, while doing their jobs in the schools, as a result of principals' behaviours towards them.

Work behaviours are so important in organizational productivity that every leader needs to be aware of this aspect of organizational functioning (El Husseini, 2024). Human resource professions also have to work on it. This is because employees' work behaviours are central to a successful and productive workplace (Crampton, 2023). Understanding work behaviours therefore, helps the managers (Saxena and Sinha, 2021) and employees to shape it to a particular direction for organizational productivity and individual wellbeing. Work behaviours can be positive or negative. Positive work behaviours include friendliness, smiling, caring, honesty, organizational citizenship, job performance, compassion, trust. Negative work behaviours include arrogance, anger, aggression, rudeness, sabotage, theft, frowning, snobbery, fighting, sulking, cheating, evasive behaviours. A positive work behaviour leads to higher productivity, team and individual performance (Thorton, 2024). Contrarily, a negative work behaviour from even an employee, can ruin the reputation of the organization, thereby harm the entire organization. This is because an individual's negative work behaviour could constitute a mirror through which a customer or customers can see the entire culture of the organization. It suggests that vice principals' work behaviours in

secondary schools in Anambra State can affect the operation of the entire secondary school system and should therefore be brought to the awareness of principals so that it could be given a crucial consideration by principals (and the entire school system).

One major way principals can influence and direct vice principals' (and other school members') work behaviours towards school productivity is through their organizational justice behaviours. Organizational justice is the fair and equitable way organizational leaders treat other members of the organization. Adewoyin (2022) sees organizational justice as the perception of workers on the decisions and practices of the managers. It includes the way the managers/leaders distribute the resources of the organization among the members (Mensah, Azila-Gbettor and Appletu, 2024), the way they reward the employees based on merits (Halliday, 2021), the way they share the workloads and even administer punishments (Efang and Akpan, 2015) among organizational members. It also includes the way they ensure that staff professional development and other needs of employees are attended to (Ofojebe and Akudo, 2021). In the secondary schools, principals' organizational justice is teachers' and other school members' feeling that principals' behaviours, decisions and actions favour them and consequently impact their own attitudes and behaviours (Conrad, 2021). Operationally, principals' organizational justice behaviour towards vice principals is therefore the manner in which principals take decisions and actions concerning vice principals, how vice principals perceive such decisions and actions as fair or unfair and how they impact vice principals' work behaviours.

Organizational justice has been majorly examined under three dimensions. These are distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice. Distributive justice is the way organizational leaders share the human and material resources of the organizations for the effective achievement of the success of the schools. It also includes the way the workloads are shared, the way rewards (including punishments) are apportioned to the employees (Efang and Ekpan, 2015, Falay, 2018). Procedural justice is the way principals handle the rewards and punishments of school members by implementing established rules, norms, and procedures of the schools. Interactional justice is the respectful, considerate and dignified way managers/leaders treat employees during the implementation of distributive and procedural justice (Ngeleshi and Dominic, 2021). In other words, it is the perception of employees that the leader has treated them with dignity and sensitivity while implementing distributive and procedural justice. When principals in secondary schools in Anambra State apply these three dimensions of organizational justice in their relationship with vice principals, they create a harmonious relationship between them and the vice principals which improves the work behaviours of vice principals. In this study, distributive justice as a dimension of principals' organizational justice behaviour which determines vice principals' (and other school members') work behaviours was examined.

Distributive justice is the oldest form of organizational justice (Kutche, 2019). It is one of the strongest organizational justice behaviours of organizational leaders that affect the behaviours of organizational employees. Distributive justice is the just and fair way organizational leaders share the human and material resources among the school members for school goal achievement. Mulgund (2022) sees distributive justice as providing every employee a fair number of resources to carry out their work. Ayadi, Zhang, Zouaoui and Ohana (2019) view distributive justice as the fairness of decision outcomes. It is how rewards and resources are allocated among employees (Mensah, Azila-Gbettor and Appletu, 2024), based on the distribution of job outcomes and job inputs (Falay, 2018). Employees' job outcomes include wages, promotion, social rights, awards, punishments, leave time, task responsibilities, physical resources, facilities for development (Falay, 2018), appointments, performance

appraisal, pay raise/rise, retrenchment decisions and equitable allocations of rewards (Kumasey, Delle and Hossain, 2019). Employees' inputs include such things as education, knowledge, skills, efforts, time, cognitive resources and performance (Falay, 2018). In secondary schools, principals' distributive justice means principals' sharing of the secondary school organizational outcomes equally among employees (Ayadi, Zhang and Zouaoui and Ohana, 2019) as well as rewarding employees' job inputs according to merits (Falay, 2018, Halliday, 2021). In the context of this study, principals' distributive justice in secondary schools in Anambra State is therefore principals' equitable sharing of school resources between vice principals and other school members and rewarding vice principals (and other school members) according to their inputs in the secondary schools in Anambra State.

Distributive justice is essential for employees' job satisfaction and participation in organizational productivity. Falay (2018) asserts that giving employees equal shares of distributed organizational resources is essential for positive attitudes and behaviours of the employees. Rhama, Tjahjono and Rahayu (2024) elucidate that providing some employees with more resources and some with less resources and expecting them to make the same profitable results is quite unreasonable. Summarily, if organizational outcomes are distributed relatively fairly, it leads to higher employees' trust in their organizations (Alshabani, Olah, Popp and Zaien, 2019), commitment and productivity. This includes such things as employees being rewarded in proportion to what their mates in the same and other organizations get (Kumasey, Delle and Hossain, 2021), being rewarded and even punished according to their contributions/merits to situations or the schools (Halliday, 2021, Mensah, Azila-Gbettor and Appletu, 2024), being provided with equal opportunity for professional development (Akudo and Ibeh, 2021), not overburdening any employee (Thorton, 2024) with heavy workloads, while other employees have little or nothing to do. These are all aspects of distributive justice that motivate employees and cause them to have positive work behaviours in their organizations. This suggests that Anambra State secondary school principals' understanding of the impact of their distributive justice behaviours on the work behaviours of vice principals (and other school members) in Anambra State is therefore of paramount importance.

In distributive justice, an employee is able to assess his or her compensation to those received by an employee who is part of the organizational context or who is doing the same work he or she does (Ouyi, 2019). In the secondary school, as a general rule, a teacher will perceive his or her equitable treatment if his remuneration (material, social and symbolic) is proportional to his or her contribution (effort, performance, time) in comparison with what he or she perceives for another reference or a previous situation (Kutche, 2019). For instance, with the same job and the same salary between two people who have the same qualification and years of experience at the same institution, job satisfaction is achieved. This is in line with Adam's equity theory (1963) principle that group behaviour depends on the distribution of organizational resources. This means that vice principals' in secondary schools in Anambra State will compare the treatment principals (and the whole school system) give them with the treatment their colleagues in other schools and organizations receive from the leaders, especially in the distribution of resources and rewarding behaviours of principals. If the treatment is in proportion to their expectations, it makes vice principals feel satisfied and connected to the principals and the entire school system and this enhances their positive work behaviours. If it does not match what their mates get, it causes vice principals to be dissatisfied and to exhibit negative work behaviours.

Generally, distributive justice has been identified as one of the most organizational justice behaviours of leaders which determine employees' behaviours. Nuzula and Nurmaya (2020)

opine that distributive justice has the most significant influence among other variables within organizational justice. This is because distributive justice determines who gets what (Subramanian, Srinkath and Thakur, 2022) and it depends on such a way that employees perceive that resources have been shared equitably and replenished adequately (Pan, Chen, Hao and Bi, 2018). According to Nuzula and Nurmaya (2020), distributive justice requires that benefits, rights and duties are distributed with consideration given to abilities and commitments. Subramanian, Srinkath and Thakur maintain that employees' perceived fairness in distributive justice evokes higher level of gratitude towards the organization among the employees. When employees within the same grade structure receive the same basic salary as a result of appropriate distribution of justice, it might stimulate their efforts to be vigorous, dedicated and absorbed (Kumasey, Delle and Hossain 2021). Thus, Adelakun (2023) summarizes that leaders' achievement of distributive justice in their organizations depends on the appropriate application of three allocations, namely, equality (to each the same), equity (to each in accordance with contribution) and need (to each in accordance with the most urgency). This implies that it may not always be easy for leaders to give employees the same amount of resources or treatment all the time. Some people may have more desperate needs for more allocation of resources, some may work harder than others. Some people may contribute more than others, while some may have urgent need to be treated differently in some situations. In spite of these distributive justice challenges, Mulgund (2022) elucidates that the decision making of leaders must be transparent so that the employees know that they are being treated fairly and understand on what basis the distribution is made and the thought process behind it. This implies that even when principals have any reason to give an employee or some employees more resources, awards, opportunities or even punishments, based on needs, they must explain to other employees the facts that necessitated such a decision so that it would not appear to other employees that they have been unfairly treated.

In the secondary schools, distributive justice is the most crucially important out of the three dimensions of organizational justice from the teachers' point of view which can be seen in different forms, from grading, giving feedback to praising and providing students with opportunities (Yang, 2021). Distributive justice is positively as well as negatively related to many personal and organizational outcomes. Distributive justice tends to be a stronger predictor of personal outcomes, job and physical level satisfaction, intent to stay in the organization (Pan, Chen, Hao and Bi, 2018). It is related to gratitude towards the organization (Subramanian, Srinkath and Thakur, 2022), trust and performance (Alshaabani, Olah, Popp and Zaien, 2019), promoting a positive environment, protecting the resources of the organization (Ouyi, 2019). It is also related to job engagement, involvement, vigour, dedication, absorption and commitment (Kumasey, Delle and Hossain, 2021), job satisfaction, quality of work-life balance and organizational effectiveness (Pan, Chen, Hao and Bi, 2018).

Contrarily, distributive justice if negatively applied leads to employee counter-productive work behaviours, such as demotivation, low enthusiasm, decreased job involvement and concentration at work (Kumasey, Delle and Hossain, 2021), dissatisfaction, aggrieved staff, complaints (Oguonu, Nwokah, and Acee-Eke, 2019), poor performance, absenteeism, tardiness, frustration, minimized efforts (Dar, 2017), job insecurity, turnover behaviours (Aliedan, Sabaih, Alyahaya and Elshaer, 2022) and unpleasant thoughts and feelings which may cause deviant behaviours (Dar, 2017). When employees perceive that there has been unjust distribution of organizational outcomes, they seek to change their performance in order to restore justice within the organization (Azubuike and Wosu, 2021).

Distributive justice has been linked to many deviant (anti-social) behaviours, such as, offensive communication, aggression, incivility, hostility (Chory, 2023), resentment, theft, vandalism, retaliation, sabotage (Dar, 2017), damage of organizational reputation (Oguonu, Nwokah and Acee-Eke, 2019) and property (Ajala, 2015). Obalade and Mtembu (2023) contend that workplace deviant behaviours of an employee may not be a part of the individual's inherent behaviours but an attempt to retaliate an unfair treatment received by performing acts that are harmful to the organization. In other words, victims of distributive injustice could get satisfaction by harming the organization in an attempt to seek equity (Obalade and Mtembu, 2023). Ajala (2015) confirms that employees' perception of unfair treatment at the workplace can cause them to venture into theft of the organization's property, waste company materials, disobey instructions and spend time on personal matters than on the organization's business. Dar (2017) corroborates that those who perceive distributive justice as unfair steal more from the organization than those who perceive it as fair. This implies that vice principals' job performance and absenteeism behaviours in Anambra State secondary schools could be influenced by principals' inability to distributive the school resources equitably or reward employees meritoriously. It therefore means that principals in Anambra State must ensure appropriate distribution of resources to avoid the elicitation of any deviant behaviour which may hinder the school progress and goal achievement in Anambra State, especially vice principals' job performance and absenteeism.

Job performance and absenteeism are two work behaviours of vice principals (or any other organizational workers) that can be strongly predicted by principals' distributive justice. Mensah, Azila-Gbettor and Appletu (2024) confirm that an employee's decision to display appropriate behaviours may be a function of how he or she perceives being fairly treated. More significantly, employees' perception of how fair resources and decision outcomes are shared/distributed, is one of the factors that influence employees' task performance (Agbim, 2021). In other words, employees' perception of unjust distribution of organizational outcomes causes them to change their performance in order to restore justice within the organization (Azubuiké and Nwosu, 2021).

Similarly, employees' absenteeism could stem from unequal distribution of resources. It should be borne in mind that absenteeism goes beyond mere physical absence of a worker during the scheduled work hours. Absenteeism includes withdrawal behaviours (Srimulyani and Hermanto, 2022), in other words, avoiding active participation in the organization's activities. It also includes spending time on personal businesses or matters than the organization's (Ajala, 2015), lack of punctuality, observance of minimum work hours (Hawks, 2023), skipping work days and faking ill to avoid work (Onyali, Njoku and Okafor, 2024), being physically present but not committed to the organization's activities (Schnaidman, 2020). Srimulyani and Hermanto (2022) posit that employees who view organizational distributive justice as low or unfair have greater tendency for withdrawal behaviours. Likewise, staff who are physically present at their job but are not committed to their students or schools (Schnaidman, 2020) are all evidence of absenteeism. When employees are not given enough or as much resources as their colleagues to do their job, when their contribution to the organization is not fairly rewarded, they may decide to while away time in the organizations. All these are absenteeism behaviours which equally affect the employees' performance and organizational productivity. Thus, Mensah, Azila-Gbettor and Appletu (2024) urge managers to support employees in engaging in positive work behaviours by exhibiting behaviours considered fair by employees. This implies that vice principals' job performance and absenteeism could be predicted by principals' distributive justice in the schools. It implies that principals in secondary schools in Anambra State have to consider

their distributive justice behaviours towards vice principals and other school members to enhance their positive work behaviours and minimize or eliminate the negative ones.

In Anambra State, numerous research studies conducted in secondary schools have shown that principals' distributive justice behaviour is one of their relationship behaviours with the school staff which has had unfavourable effects on staff work behaviours, particularly staff job performance and absenteeism. Thompson and Unachukwu (2020) bewail that principals' ability to treat all employees equally in the schools seems to be a systemic illusion. This ranges from discrimination, prejudice, favouritism, inequality in performance appraisal and rewarding of staff (Ihueze, Unachukwu and Onyali, 2018). Whereas it is not fair to overburden any employee (Thorton, 2024), there is assignment of heavy workload to some staff without any motivation (Okeke, Okaforcha and Ezinine, 2021), assignment of heavy workload to some staff, while some other staff are given very little of nothing to do (Njoku, Onyali and Ogbo, 2024, Onyali, Njoku and Okafor, 2024) to lack of interest and inability to provide resources for staff professional development (Akudo and Ibeh, 2021, Ewim, Unachukwu and Ugwu, 2020). Ewim, Unachukwu and Ugwu confirmed in their study that some teachers are not being sponsored for workshops, conferences and other in-service training courses. These negative organizational justice behaviours of principals which militate against the principles of distributive justice have negatively affected staff job performance in Anambra State (Ihueze, Unachukwu and Onyali, 2018).

Similarly, employees' absenteeism seems to be affected by these behaviours too. For instance, Arinze, Egboka and Nwosu (2024) and Ezeugbor and Eboatu (2018) noted that some teachers absent themselves from school without any fair reason or official permission. There is poor punctuality habit, irregular attendance to classes and persistent lateness to work among staff (Nwagbata, 2024, Ewim, Unachukwu and Ugwu, 2020). Ezeugbor and Eboatu bitterly bewail that the rate of truancy and general performance of the staff with the overt carefree attitudes of teachers are issues of major concerns in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Some teachers who are present in the school remain in the staff room, gossiping instead of attending to their classes (Ewim, Unachukwu and Ugwu, 2020, Ezeugbor and Eboatu, 2018). There are also cases of absenteeism and poor job performance attitudes and behaviours, even among some vice principals, evidenced in their cold attitude, aloofness and indifference towards the schools' activities as a result of bad relationship of principals, especially poor organizational justice behaviours of principals (Onyali, Njoku and Okafor, 2024). Onyali, Njoku and Okafor further noted that some principals assign vice principals' statutory job responsibilities to some other staff without giving any explanation to vice principals for such delegations. This wrong delegation of principals could increase the workload of such staff and deprive vice principals of the appropriate allocation of their statutory workloads in their job responsibilities, causing them to feel frustrated and while away time in the schools. All these behaviours negatively affect school productivity. Principals' distributive justice could therefore, constitute a source of these negative behaviours among the staff. Principals in secondary schools in Anambra State should therefore understand the implications of their distributive justice behaviours on the work behaviours of the school members, especially vice principals. When principals' distributive justice in the schools is fair, it boosts the work behaviours of school staff. When it is unfair, it also affects their work behaviours. Meanwhile, there is a dearth of empirical studies in Anambra State that have tried to examine if principals' distributive justice impacts their relationship with vice principals and how this impact has been measured on vice principals' job performance and absenteeism behaviours. Thus arises the question, "Could principals' distributive justice be a source of vice principals' work behaviours, especially vice principals' "

job performance and absenteeism behaviours in public secondary schools in Anambra State”? The quest to unravel the answer to this question, was the factor that motivated the researchers to delve into this research work.

Statement of the Problem

Public understanding of distributive justice and improving it because of its impact on employees’ work behaviours, has increased in the recent times, with America topping the lead (Rhama, Tjahjono and Rahayu, 2024). Creating this awareness in Nigeria, particularly among secondary school principals in Anambra State is crucial. When organizational resources are equitably shared, workloads, rewards (and punishments) fairly administered by leaders, they form strong distributive organizational justice behaviours which lead to employees’ satisfaction and commitment. In the secondary schools, when principals apply distributive justice well, it leads to staff satisfaction and positive work behaviours. When there is an unfair application of distributive justice, it equally leads to dissatisfaction among employees which invariably affects their work behaviours.

In Anambra State, principals’ organizational justice is an area that has been very vastly researched by scholars and researchers. It has been empirically proved that principals’ distributive justice in Anambra State is poor. There is, for instance, discrimination, prejudice, favouritism, inequality in performance appraisal and rewarding of staff. Workloads are not evenly distributed. For instance, some staff are given heavy workloads without extra rewards, while others are given little or neglected in the assignment of workloads. There is hardly any provision for staff professional development, such as attending conferences, workshops, and other in-service trainings. Some staff are not involved in the decision makings of the principals. There is inequitable delegation of duties, especially between vice principals and other school members. Some principals assign vice principals’ jobs to other school members without any explanation for such assignment. This causes work overload on some staff, while others have work under-load. These are some of the negative distributive justice behaviours of principals which affect staff work behaviours in the schools. These behaviours have immensely affected staff job performance and absenteeism in Anambra State. However, no work carried out in Anambra State has associated vice principals as a group or individual staff whose work behaviours are affected by principals’ poor distributive justice. The dearth of any empirical work on principals’ distributive justice and vice principals’ work behaviours, specifically, vice principals’ job performance and absenteeism in Anambra State stimulated the interest of the researchers to conduct this study in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The problem of the study was stated thus, “What is the predictive relationship between principals’ distributive justice and vice principals’ work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State?”

Method

A correlational research design was used in the study. One research question and one hypothesis were stipulated. The population of the study was all the principals and vice principals in the 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The census sampling technique was used to draw a population of 532 vice principals, made up of 266 vice principals administration and 266 vice principals academics in the 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two instruments, namely, “Principals’ Organizational Justice Scale for Vice Principals (POJSVP) and Vice Principals’ Work Behaviours Scale (VPWBS)” were used to collect data. POJSVP was adopted and used to collect data on principals’ distributive justice, while VPWBS was constructed by the researchers and used to collect data

on vice principals' work behaviours. The two instruments were submitted for face validity to three research experts in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka. The instruments were thereafter administered on twenty(20) vice principals in public secondary schools in Enugu State. The Cronbach alpha reliability test was used in the analysis to determine the reliability coefficient. This yielded an average reliability coefficient of 0.86. The researchers involved four research assistants from the six education zones in Anambra State who assisted them in the administration of the instruments. A total of 532 copies of the instruments were administered on the population. 521 (98%) were fully filled and retrieved. These were used for data analysis. The simple regression analysis was used, where: 0 – 0.1 = weak, 0.2 – 0.3 = modest, 0.4 – 0.5 = moderate, > 0.5 = strong prediction. P-value was used to determine the significance of the prediction for the hypothesis. Where the calculated p-value was less than the stipulated level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis was rejected. The null hypothesis was not rejected where the calculated p-value was greater than the stipulated level of significance (0.05).

Results

Research Question: What is the predictive value of principals' distributive justice on vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1. Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of Principals' Distributive Justice as a Predictor of Vice Principals' Work Behaviours in secondary Schools in Anambra State

	R	R ²	Adj.R ²	B	SE B	B
Constant				16.94	1.22	
Distributive Justice	.71	.50	.50	.189	.08	.71

Data in Table 1 indicates that principals' distributive justice is a moderate predictor of vice principals' work behaviours in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is shown by the regression coefficient (R = .71) and the coefficient of determination (R² = .50).

Hypothesis: Principals' distributive justice does not significantly predict vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 2: Significance of Simple Regression Analysis of Principals' Distributive Justice as a Predictor of Vice Principals' Work Behaviours in Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Predictor	R	R ²	F(1,542)	p-value	Decision
Distributive Justice	.71	.50	532.94	.000	Significant

The simple regression result displayed in Table 2 shows that principals' distributive justice is a significant predictor of vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State, R = .71, F (1,542) = 532.94 and p-value <0.05. Since the obtained p-value was less than stipulated level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion

The Predictive Value of Principals' Distributive Justice on Vice Principals' Work Behaviours in Secondary Schools in Anambra State

The result of the study in Table 1 shows that principals' distributive justice is a moderate and significant predictor of vice principals' work behaviours. Its significance is shown in Table 2 of the summary of the analysis. The findings of this study disagrees with the result of Srivata (2015)'s study that distributive justice had no predictive relationship on workers' job satisfaction. It is also consistent with Nuzula and Nurmaya (2020) whose study on distributive justice found no correlation between distributive justice and organizational citizenship behaviours. The difference in the findings of the two studies might be as a result of the difference in the population, location and time of the studies. Srivasta conducted her study on health workers in India almost a decade ago, while the present study is on school principals and vice principals in Nigeria. Similarly, Nuzula and Nurmaya conducted their study on employees of a telecommunication company in Indonesia, while the present study was conducted on vice principals of public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. However, the finding supports Alshaabani, Olah, Popp and Zaien (2019), Thompson and Unachukwu (2020)'s studies that objective distribution of material and human resources in school is a significant predictor of workers' behaviours. The results of the study also justifies Mulgund (2022)'s contention that giving unequal amount of resources to employees and expecting them to achieve equal results is unfair. In other words, when organizational resources are shared relatively fairly, it boosts employees' satisfaction and work behaviours (Alshabani, Olah, Popp and Zaien, 2019). It implies that vice principals' negative work behaviours in Anambra State will change if principals apply distributive justice as a dimension of their relationship with them.

Conclusion

Principals' distributive justice is a moderate predictor of vice principals' work behaviours. In other words, principals' ability to equitably share the resources of the schools and administer rewards or even punishment between vice principals and other school members influence vice principals' work behaviours.

Recommendations

1. Principals should share the resources of the school between vice principals and other school members in a fair manner.
2. Principals should reward the staff by merit.
3. Principals should encourage vice principals (and other staff) to develop themselves professionally by providing them with the assistance they need.

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